

Peer Review Journal

ISSN 1817-5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of The Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 2 Number 1 March 2006

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Ali Hassan Al Shimari
Minister of Health

Founding Editor: Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi
Member World Association of Medical Editors

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index Medicus

Copyright Iraqi Ministry of Health

Silk granuloma:Editorial commentary.

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi MD,PhD.
Consultant physician
Editor in chief,
The N Iraqi J Med
University Hospital in Al Kadhymiyia

In this issue of The New Iraqi journal of Medicine,Dr Al Rawaf reported his endoscopic experience with stitch (silk granuloma) at gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma following duodenal ulcer operations.Dr Al Rawaf was too late in his decision to publish the observation he made during the years 1986 and 1987.However,I have made clear that the policy of this journal is to publish papers that could add something to the body of the available literature. Searching the PubMed for stitch granuloma,suture granuloma,and silk granuloma it was possible to find only 14 relevant papers [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14]published during over 30 years period. Stitch granuloma have been reported following pediatric herniotomy[1,2], after thyroid surgery[3],and colorectal surgery [4,5,6],and following radical retropubic prostatectomy, and after an appendectomy [14].

The observation of Dr Al Rawaf that stitch granuloma associated mostly with the use of silk agrees with report of Kronborg O.who suggested that the use of polyglycolic acid (Dexon) instead of silk for fascial closure of abdominal incisions would reduce the rate of granulomas without an accompanying increase in rate of wound dehiscences. The two sutures were evaluated in a triple blind, randomized

trial, using the paired sample principle in patients subjected to elective gastrointestinal surgery. One gram of Pentrexyl powder was applied to the subfascial space in all the patients and the wounds were examined 10 days, 1 and 3 months after the operations. The trial was terminated when a closed sequential analysis had shown a significantly higher rate of dehiscences after closure with silk (12/163) than after closure with polyglycolic acid (1/163). Seven patients had granulomas after silk and one after polyglycolic acid at that time. Postoperative wound infections occurred in 7 patients after silk and 8 after polyglycolic acid. Kronborg O concluded that the use of polyglycolic acid (Dexon) nearly eliminates the risk of suture-granulomas, without increasing the risk of wound dehiscences; on the contrary, the rate of dehiscences was lower after polyglycolic acid[4].

In one retrospective 10-year study of herniotomies performed by a pediatric surgical service. Twenty children developed stitch granulomas following herniotomy. In all cases, silk sutures had been used in the repair. Masses appeared 1-10 years following surgery and were demonstrated by preoperative US in 17 patients, by CT alone in 1 patient and by both CT and US in 2 patients [2].To my

knowledge this is the first paper reporting the occurrence of silk granuloma at gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma following duodenal ulcer operations.

References

1-Nagar H, Kessler A, Graif M. The role of ultrasound in the diagnosis of stitch granulomas following paediatric herniotomy. *Pediatr Radiol.* 1999 Nov;29(11):803-6.

2-Nagar H. Stitch granulomas following inguinal herniotomy: a 10-year review. *J Pediatr Surg.* 1993 Nov;28(11):1505-7.

3-Eldridge PR, Wheeler MH. Stitch granulomata after thyroid surgery. *Br J Surg.* 1987 Jan;74(1):62.

4- Kronborg O. Polyglycolic acid (Dexon) versus silk for fascial closure of abdominal incisions. *Acta Chir Scand.* 1976;142(1):9-12.

5-Sanders I, Woesner ME. "Stitch" granuloma: a consideration in the differential diagnosis of the intramural gastric tumor. Case report. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 1972 Jun;57(6):558-62.

6-Belleza NA, Lowman RM. Suture granuloma of the stomach following total colectomy. *Radiology.* 1978 Apr;127(1):84.

7-Baba K, Nagao K, Matsuda M, Nishimura R, et al. An operative case of suture-granuloma which resulted from an intrapulmonary treatment 10 years ago and manifested hemoptysis]

Kyobu Geka. 1996 Nov;49(12):1048-51. Japanese

8-Carroll KM, Sairam K, Olliff SP, Wallace DM. Case report: paravesical suture granuloma resembling bladder carcinoma on CT scanning. *Br J Radiol.* 1996 May;69(821):476-8.

9-Brunsvold MA, Reding ME, Kornman KS. Infected suture granuloma: a case report. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 1991 Summer;6(2):215-7.

10-Scheidler DM, Foster RS, Bihle R, Scott JW, Litwiller SE. Anastomotic suture granuloma following radical retropubic prostatectomy. *J Urol.* 1990 Jan;143(1):133-4.

11-Muzafer M. Silk granuloma. *Br J Clin Pract.* 1985 Sep;39(9):367-8.

12-Manor A, Kaffe I. Unusual foreign body reaction to a braided silk suture: a case report. *J Periodontol.* 1982 Feb;53(2):86-8.

13-Marcus VA, Roy I, Sullivan JD, Sutton JR. Necrobiotic palisading suture granulomas involving bone and joint: report of two cases. *Am J Surg Pathol.* 1997 May;21(5):563-5.

14-A case of suture granuloma occurring 25 years after an appendectomy. *J Dermatol.* 2003 Aug;30(8):634-6. Ichimiya M, Hamamoto Y, Muto M.